

ISic0643

I.Sicily inscription 0643

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

cippus

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Styella

Place of origin (modern)

Pedagaggi

Provenance

'nella piccola pianura sottostante il borgo, nel corso di lavori'

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Pedagoggi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332942

1. Μ (ἄρκος) Βαλήρις
2. Μαρκα-
3. ρίων ἔ-
4. ζησ [ε]
5. ἔτη ν', [μῆ]-
6. νες η' [—(?)].
- 7.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644885

PHI 332942

Bibliography

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1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 44.0770

Manganaro, G. 1994. Iscrizioni, epigrafi ed epigrammi in Greco della Sicilia orientale di epoca romana. *Mélanges de l'École Française de Rome: Antiquité.* 106: 79-118. At 89 no.7 fig.10

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